

Mixed-Ligand Complexes : Part IV. Biguanide Bis Ethylenediamine Cobalt (III) Complexes

R. L. Dutta

Biguanide reacts with *trans* dichloro bis ethylenediamine Cobalt(III) in aqueous solution to provide heterochelate complex $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})(\text{en})_2]\text{X}_2$, where X represents a univalent anion. The complexes are highly soluble and provide normal values for conductance and equivalent weight. The electronic absorption spectra gives the two bands representing the transitions

While working in the broad field of mixed ligand complexes of Cobalt(III), we had already reported a large group of such complexes containing two biguanide ligands inside the coordination zone¹. Complexes $[\text{Co}(\text{AA})(\text{en})_2]\text{X}_2$ have been reported where AA is acetylacetonate, dithiooxalate, glycine and other optically active amino acids, O-phenanthroline etc. etc.²⁻⁶. Coming in this series, we have now introduced a bidentate biguanide along with two ethylenediamine ligands.

On treating *trans* dichloro bis ethylenediamine Cobalt(III) chloride in aqueous solution with biguanide around pH 7-8, no immediate change could be noticed. However on warming on a steam bath the purple coloured solution changed to deep red indicating replacement of the unidentate groups inside the coordination zone.

Isolation of salts of the heterochelate cation proved quite difficult. On treating the above concentrated solution with a strong ammonium sulphate followed by KI, glistening needles appeared, which could be further purified by recrystallisation from hot water. This was identified as a mixed anion salt, $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH})\text{en}_2]\text{ISO}_4$. The only other salt that could be crystallised from solution was the iodide.

1. Dutta and Sarkar, this series of papers, this *Journal*, under publication.
2. Werner and Matlissen, *Helv. Chem. Acta*, 1918, 1, 78.
3. Werner, Schwyzer and Karrer, *ibid.*, 1921, 4, 115.
4. Hidaka and Douglas, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1964, 3, 1724.
5. Hidaka and Douglas, *ibid.*, 1964, 3, 1180.
6. Liu and Douglas, *ibid.*, 1964, 3, 1356.

Our earlier premonition that biguanide may bring about a complex disproportionation into tris biguanide Cobalt(III) and tris ethylenediamine Cobalt(III) was thus proved untrue. O-Phenanthroline, which occupies a position in the spectrochemical series far closer to the cyanide end than the ethylenediamine has also slipped in without any rancour inside the coordination zone².

The iodide salt was studied for its conductance at various dilutions. These values were found to be normal and come close to the expected range of tri-univalent electrolytes¹. Besides, equivalent weight of the iodide salt was also determined by stripping the aqueous solution through a cation exchanger (H⁺ form) and estimating the liberated acid. (Found : 160; Required : 167).

TABLE I

Conductance measurements in aqueous solution at 20°.

[Co(BigH)(en) ₂] ₃ I ₃ Dilutions (in litres)	128	256	512	1024	
Λ^0	102.3	116.0	119.9	128.0	
Λ^∞	121.1	131.0	130.8	136.1	
(mean) Λ^∞	139.6	Molar conductance = 418.8 mhos. cm ² mole ⁻¹ .			

The absorption spectra was scanned within the range 320 m μ to 550 m μ . As expected, the complex shows two absorption bands, one at 350-360 m μ and the other at 480-490 m μ . For comparison, we include the bands of [Co(BigH)₃]³⁺ and [Co(en)₃]³⁺, which shows a slight shift thus indicating biguanide to throw almost as strong a ligand field as ethylenediamine.

TABLE II

Electronic Absorption Spectra of some Cobalt(III) heterochelate.

Complex	λ max. (m μ)	Band II		λ max. (m μ)	Band I	
		ν , cm ⁻¹	Molar ϵ		ν , cm ⁻¹	Molar ϵ
1. [Co(en) ₃]Cl ₃	340	29,400	65	470	21,300	72.5
2. [Co(BigH)(en) ₂][SO ₄] ₃	350	28,600	132	480- 490	20,800	158
3. [Co(BigH) ₃](SO ₄) ₃	350	28,600	187	475- 480	21,100- 20,800	207
4. [Co(BigH) ₃]Cl ₃	350- 355	28,600- 28,200	220	475	21,100	235

The spectra of the [Co(BigH)₃](SO₄)₃ and [Co(BigH)₃]Cl₃ have both been included to examine the influence of the anions on the absorption spectra.

The abnormally high solubility did not make possible isolation of salts with optically active anions like d-tartrate or camphor sulphonate. This made difficult any attempt towards resolution.

EXPERIMENTAL

Biguanide acid sulphate⁸ and trans dichloro bis ethylenediamine Cobalt(III) chloride⁹ were prepared by standard methods.

1. *Biguanide bis ethylenediamine Cobalt(III) iodide sulphate* : Trans dichloro bis ethylenediamine Cobalt(III) chloride (2.8 gm.) was added to an aqueous, slightly alkaline solution of biguanide acid sulphate (2.2 gm. in about 50 ml. water) and the mixture warmed on a steam bath. The initial dark purple colour of the solution gradually changed to blood red. The solution was neutralised with dilute H₂SO₄, filtered and the filtrate treated with KI. Large crop of maroon red crystals separated and these were recrystallised from a small volume of hot water as glistening needles. {Found : Co, 11.6 ; N, 25.8 ; SO₄, 18.9 ; I, 24.8%. [Co(BigH)(en)₂]I SO₄ requires, Co, 11.8 ; N, 25.2 ; I, 19.0 ; SO₄, 25%}.

2. *Biguanide bis ethylenediamine Cobalt(III) iodide* : Biguanide sulphate (2.2 gm. in about 50 ml. water) was treated with barium chloride (2.4 gm. in 10 ml. water), warmed and then filtered. The filtrate was made slightly alkaline and was treated with trans dichloro bis ethylenediamine Cobalt(III) chloride (2.8 gm.). The solution was heated on a steam bath till reduced to a small volume (about 20 ml.) neutralised with dilute HCl and cooled. The solution was treated with KI and cooled further. Dark red crystals separated. These were filtered and recrystallised from a small volume of hot water and finally recovered as dark red shining crystals. {Found : Co, 8.7 ; N, 19.0 ; I, 58.4%. [Co(BigH)(en)₂]I₃ requires, Co, 8.9 ; N, 19.1 ; I, 57.8%}.

All experimental techniques are the same as described in the earlier parts of this series of studies.

This is a pleasure to record with appreciation the ungrudging assistance in respect of some instrumental measurements that I had received from my student Dr. A. Syamal.

INORGANIC CHEMISTRY LABORATORY,
THE UNIVERSITY OF BURDWAN,
BURDWAN, WEST BENGAL (INDIA).

Received, May 16, 1966.

8. Inorganic Syntheses, Vol. VI, p. 65.

9. Inorganic Syntheses, Vol. II, p. 223.